

Speculation on $q \approx 1$ Tsallis $\ln_q(p) \approx \ln(p) * MB$ distribution Scenario

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In (1), we noted that by using an Euler infinite product expansion to describe the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p) = 1/2k (p^k - p^{-k})$ one obtains in the $k \ll 1$ limit, with $0 < k < 1$: $\ln_k(p) = \ln(p) \exp\{kk \ln(p)\ln(p)/6\}$ or $\exp(-kk \ln(p)\ln(p)/6)$ $\ln_k(p) = \ln(p)$. In other words, $\ln(p)$ may be associated with a statistical unnormalized Gaussian multiplied by $\ln_k(p)$ in this limit. We suggested that this might yield some statistical insight into the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p)$.

Here we consider the Tsallis $\ln_q(p)$ for $q \approx 1$ in the same manner and find: $\ln_q(p) = \ln(p) \exp(.5 (1-q) \ln(p))$. If $q=1+\delta$ ($\delta > 0$ but tiny), then the exponent is positive, while if $q=1-\delta$, the exponent is negative. One sees that an unnormalized Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is linked with $\ln_q(p)$ just as a Gaussian is linked with $\ln_k(p)$ Kaniadakis. Thus, it seems that the Kaniadakis case is linked with $\ln(p)$ and a Gaussian in $\ln(p)$ and the Tsallis case with an MB distribution and $\ln(p)$ in the $k \ll 1$ and $q \approx 1$ limits.

Tsallis and Kaniadakis $q=1$ and $k=0$ limits.

In the $q=1$ limit, the Tsallis $\ln_q(p) = \ln(p)$ and $\{1+(1-q)(-e^{-i}/T)\}$ power $1/(1-q)$ becomes $\exp(-e^{-i}/T)$. In the $k=0$ limit, the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p) = \ln(p)$ and $\{-ke^{-i}/T + \sqrt{1+kke^{-i}/T}\}$ power k becomes $\exp(-e^{-i}/T)$. We are interested, however, in the $k \ll 1$ limit for $0 < k < 1$ and the $q \approx 1$ limits.

In (1), we used an Euler infinite product representation of $\ln_k(p)$ to show that:

$$\ln_k(p) = \ln(p) \exp(kk \ln(p)\ln(p)/6) \text{ for } k \ll 1 \quad ((1))$$

It is not necessary to use this Euler infinite product to obtain this result as:

$$\ln_k(p) = 1/2k \{ p^k - p^{-k} \} \approx \ln(p) + \frac{1}{6} kk \ln(p)\ln(p)\ln(p) + \dots \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{For } k \ll 1, \ln_k(p) \approx \ln(p) \exp(kk \ln(p)\ln(p)/6) \quad ((3))$$

Given that $\ln(p) < 0$ for $0 < p < 1$ (even if p is unnormalized) one may write:

$$\ln_k(p) \exp(-kk \ln(p)\ln(p)/6) = \ln(p) \quad ((4))$$

In other words, $\ln(p)$ is linked with $\ln_k(p)$ multiplied by an unnormalized Gaussian in $\ln(p)$. We suggest that a Gaussian has a statistical interpretation (maximum randomness in $\ln(p)$) and that this might shed some light on the meaning of the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p)$. We now try to extend these ideas to the Tsallis $\ln_q(p)$.

$$\ln_q(p) = 1/(1-q) \{ p^{(1-q)} - 1 \} \approx \ln(p) \{ 1 + .5 \ln(p) (1-q) + \dots \} \quad ((5)) \text{ for } q \approx 1$$

$$\text{Or } \ln_q(p) \approx \ln(p) \exp(.5 (1-q) \ln(p)) \quad ((6))$$

We notice first that $\exp(.5(1-q) \ln(p))$ is of the form of a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in $\ln(p)$ unlike a Gaussian as in the Kaniadakis case.

If $q=1+\delta$ ($\delta>0$ and tiny), then the exponent of \exp in ((6)) is positive if $\ln(p)<0$ which holds for $0<p<1$, even if p is unnormalized. If $q=1-\delta$, then the exponent of \exp is negative. Thus:

$$q=1+\delta: \ln q(p) \exp(.5(1-q)\ln(p)) = \ln(p) \quad ((7a))$$

$$q=1-\delta: \ln k(p) = \ln(p) \exp(.5(1-q) \ln(p)) \quad ((7b))$$

Thus, the Tsallis case seems to link $\ln q(p)$ or $\ln(p)$ with a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution while the Kaniadakis case is linked to a Gaussian in the variable $\ln(p)$.

In other words, both the Kaniadakis and Tsallis distributions associated a distribution to the variable $\ln(p)$ which is used to link $\ln k(p)=-e_i/T$ or $\ln q(p) = -e_i/T$ to $\ln(p)$ in the $k\ll 1$ or q approx 1 limits.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Tsallis and Kaniadakis formalisms reduce to the Shannon formalism in the $q=1$ or $k=0$ limits. We thus try to see how they deviate for $k\ll 1$ or q approx=1. In the Shannon case, $\ln(p) = -e_i/T$ (the physical and statistical key informational parameter), but in the Kaniadakis case, $\ln k(p) = -e_i/T$ while in the Tsallis, $\ln q(p) = -e_i/T$. It seems that in the $k\ll 1$ limit, $\ln k(p) \exp(-kk\ln(p)\ln(p)/6) = \ln(p)$. Thus, there is a Gaussian in the variable $\ln(p)$ associated with $\ln k(p)$ and we showed in (1) that this enhanced the value of p for large $-e_i/T$ (i.e. there is less of a drop than for $\exp(-e_i/T)$).

Here we show that if $q=1+\delta$ ($\delta>0$), then $\ln q(p) \exp(.5(1-q) \ln(p)) = \ln(p)$, i.e. a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is linked with $\ln q(p)$ and $\ln(p)$. The distribution is in the variable $\ln(p)$. If $q=1-\delta$, then $\ln q(p) = \ln(p) \exp(.5(1-q) \ln(p))$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on the Meaning of the Kaniadakis $\ln k(p)$ for Small k (preprint, zenodo, 2025)